

the disease, except for Liao-Feng 4. RTBV alone usually was observed on resistant varieties, except Utri Rajapan (Table 1). Even when the viruliferous insects were increased, infected plants of tungro-resistant varieties usually con-

tained RTBV alone, with the exception of Utri Rajapan (Table 2). Infected resistant varieties developed milder symptoms and were not a virus source for the spread of RTV. □

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GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Screening for resistance to rice hispa

P. Chand and J.B. Tomar, Birsa Agricultural University, Kanke, Ranchi, India 834006

Rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera* (Oliv.) is a sporadic insect pest of transplanted rice. Adult beetles cause parallel white streaks on the leaf. The grubs are leaf miners and cause leaf tissue to wither. In 1983 kharif an unusual outbreak of rice hispa occurred in Ranchi.

To screen for resistance to rice hispa, we planted 64 cultivars of diverse origin in 2 replications in 1.6- × 5-m plots at 20- × 15-cm spacing. Percent leaves damaged was recorded from 25 randomly selected plants from each plot. Leaf damage ranged from 15.6 to 97%. OR165-94-1 (15.6% damage) and KAU1945 (18.6% damage) were moderately resistant (see table). □

Resistance of rice to rice hispa, Bihar, India.

Score ^a	Damage (%)	Variety
0	No damage	—
1	1-10	—
3	11-20	OR165-94-1, KAU1945
5	21-35	MTU6637, CR341-5-10, NRL326-3, UPR81-44, NDR312, OR79-21, OR158-7-1, RP52-2, RP1848-01-3-2-1, RP1846-219-3-1, BK670, HPU804, RP1575-636-6-1, Rewa 353, RP1442-4-3-1-2, RP1575-243-719-681
7	36-50	NDU127, OR131-5-8, KAU23332-2, FH448, CO 33-83, CN834-1-7-1-2, RP1895-2-1, IR36, UPR254-24-1-1, AS19789, KD5-2-8, NDU83, OR196-2, RP1788-43-2-1-6-2, NDU80, NDR301, RP1888-1441-56-4456, BIET236, UPR79-104, BAU4090-1, Ratna, RP1699-175-112-1, BR1235, RP1831-25-2-2, UPR103-44-2, RP1388-494-145, SKL-6, UPR96-40-2, UPR79-161, Rasi, HKR1, CR268-400-5, HKR78-31, RP1570-44-1, UPR79-123, RGL-2624, RP1699-26-1-1, RAU4056-53-5, NSRP11, RP1699-174-97-1, RP1699-183-133-1, RP1831-20-4-5, RP1898-6, Pusa 245-1-17-1, NDR302, KR10-47.
9	50-100	

^a0-9 scale: 0 = resistant, 9 = susceptible.

Screening rice varieties for resistance to whitebacked planthopper

A. Kartohardjono, Pests and Disease Department; and T. Suwito, Plant Breeding Department, Bogor Research Institute for Food Crops (BORIF), Bogor, Indonesia

Whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* is a serious rice pest in Indonesia. We screened 206 breeding lines for WBPH resistance at the BORIF greenhouse in 1982-83 wet seasons.

A seedbox screening test was used and lines were scored by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice (see table). The 33

Performance of 9 lines with resistance to whitebacked planthopper, Bogor, Indonesia.^a

Line	Score ^b	Eggs laid ^c (no.)	Insects (no.) on the plant ^d		
			1 DI	2 DI	3 DI
B3728d-pn-39-3-2	3	11.2 a	8.3 d	10.0 b	8.5 b
B5198b-84-Mr-3	3	13.8 a	7.3 cd	2.0 a	2.5 a
B3825e-Kn-45-2-3	3	11.2 a	7.0 bcd	3.3 a	3.0 a
B3894-17c-Sm-54-2	3	10.8 a	7.3 bcd	4.8 a	4.3 ab
B4032d-Mr-1-3-1	3	13.0 a	3.5 ab	4.8 a	2.5 a
IR5657-33-2-2-3	3	24.8 b	5.0 abcd	3.8 a	5.3 b
IR13240-102-2-Mr-6	3	12.6 a	6.8 abcd	4.0 a	2.3 a
IR5853-198-1-Mr-3-2	3	10.0 a	3.8 abc	4.5 a	1.5 a
IR5853-198-1-Mr-3-3	3	10.6 a	3.8 abc	4.8 a	3.8 a
TN1 (susceptible check)	9	38.6 c	11.8 a	12.0 b	13.5 c
Colombo (resistant check)	3	—	—	—	—
Rathu Heenathi (resistant check)	3	11.2 a	3.25	3.0 a	1.0 a

^aMeans in a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 0.05 level.

^bScoring by Standard Evaluation System for Rice: 0 = highly resistant, 9 = susceptible. ^cAv of 5 replications. ^dAv of 4 replications. DI = days after infestation.